

Synthesis, characterisation and antimicrobial activity of metal complexes of *N*-(1-piperidinobenzyl)acetamide

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Solid complexes of a new Mannich base *N*-(1-piperidinobenzyl)acetamide (PBA) with Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} have been synthesised. The complexes exhibit two types of stoichiometry, viz. [MX₂L(H₂O)₂] and [MX₂L₂] (X = Cl, Br and NO₃) in which PBA acts as a bidentate ligand coordinating through the oxygen of acetamide and nitrogen of piperidine moieties. Preliminary result shows that the ligand and complexes possess antimicrobial activities.

Acetamide and related compounds have been investigated in detail for their donor properties and biological activities¹. The present work reports on the synthesis of *N*-(1-piperidinobenzyl)acetamide (1), its complexation characteristics with Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} salts and their antimicrobial activity.

Results and Discussion

All the solid complexes are stable at room temperature, and soluble in DMF and DMSO but insoluble in common organic solvents. They decompose above 200°. The elemental analysis data (Table 1) reveal a stoichiometry of 1 : 1 (M : L) for all the complexes except the Mn^{II} nitrate, Cu^{II} nitrate and Ni^{II} bromo complexes which exhibit 1 : 2 ratio. The non-electrolytic nature of the complexes is discerned by the molar conductance values (4.64–34.83 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹)².

Infrared spectra : The ir bands of the ligand (PBA) observed at 3311, 1642, 1595 and 1161 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to ν_{as}(NH), amide I (ν_{C=O}), amide II (δ_{N-H} + ν_{C=N}) and ν_{C-N-C} of piperidine group respectively³. In all the complexes, the amide I and ν_{C-N-C} of piperidine bands displayed substantial negative shifts with fairly low intensity, indicating coordination through the oxygen of amide moiety and nitrogen of piperidine entity present in the ligand. In the spectra of all the complexes, the ν_{N-H} band remained at the same position as in the free ligand, indicating that the secondary nitrogen is not coordinated. Some of the complexes (Table 1) showed either a broad band or a double hump at 3450–3000 cm⁻¹ followed by sharp peaks at 850–820 and 650–620 cm⁻¹ attributed to stretching, rocking and wagging modes respectively of coordinated water molecules⁴. The band due to bending mode of coordinated water (around 1640 cm⁻¹) overlapped with the strong carbonyl absorption band. The presence of lattice water in cobalt(II)-chloro complex is indicated by the presence of characteristic broad contour around 3500 cm⁻¹ and a medium band around 1620 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{OH} and δ_{HOH} modes respectively of water molecule, although these can

not be claimed with certainty to show whether water molecules are coordinated or not. Isothermal mass-loss occurring at 110–130° equivalent to two water molecules is interpreted as the loss of hygroscopic water during drying of the complex. The bands at about 850 and 630 cm⁻¹ assignable to coordinated water are absent in the spectrum of this cobalt-chloro complex. In all the nitrate complexes except the nickel(II)-nitrate complex, the anion exhibits unidentate coordination since (ν₄-ν₁) is about 60–100 cm⁻¹. The ν₂ band was seen around 1050 cm⁻¹. The bidentate nitrate group⁵ of the Ni^{II} complex showed ν₄, ν₁ and ν₂ bands at 1505, 1309 and 990 cm⁻¹ respectively, in which (ν₄-ν₁) is 196 cm⁻¹. Normally the difference for a bidentate nitrate group will be around 185 cm⁻¹.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes*

Compd**	Metal % : Found/ (Calcd.)	Λ _M Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	10Dq cm ⁻¹	B' cm ⁻¹	B% -	LFSE kcal mol ⁻¹	μ _{eff} B.M.
[MnCl ₂ .PBA.(H ₂ O) ₂]	13.56(13.95)	15.60	-	-	-	-	5.86
[Mn(NO ₃) ₂ .PBA] ₂	8.72(8.55)	34.83	-	-	-	-	5.77
[CoCl ₂ .PBA].H ₂ O	15.04(14.81)	12.80	4043	641	34	13.86	4.62
[CoBr ₂ .PBA]	13.32(13.07)	8.66	-	-	-	-	4.54
[Co(NO ₃) ₂ .PBA]	14.62(14.20)	6.05	4138	635	35	14.19	4.52
[NiCl ₂ .PBA.(H ₂ O) ₂]	14.28(14.77)	12.62	8772	778	25	30.07	3.33
[NiBr ₂ .PBA] ₂	13.46(13.12)	28.20	-	-	-	-	3.20
[Ni(NO ₃) ₂ .PBA]	14.58(14.16)	10.46	8928	793	24	30.61	3.22
[CuCl ₂ .PBA.(H ₂ O) ₂]	15.40(15.79)	16.20	14084	-	-	24.14	1.82
[CuBr ₂ .PBA.(H ₂ O) ₂]	12.93(12.85)	10.41	15214	-	-	26.08	1.91
[Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .PBA] ₂	9.50(9.75)	8.20	13820	-	-	23.69	2.02
[ZnCl ₂ .PBA]	17.92(17.75)	14.62	-	-	-	-	-
[ZnBr ₂ .PBA]	14.06(14.30)	8.40	-	-	-	-	-
[Zn(NO ₃) ₂ .PBA.(H ₂ O) ₂]	14.44(14.29)	20.43	-	-	-	-	-
[CdCl ₂ .PBA]	27.28(27.06)	16.42	-	-	-	-	-
[Cd(NO ₃) ₂ .PBA]	24.42(24.00)	4.64	-	-	-	-	-
[HgCl ₂ .PBA]	40.62(39.84)	16.27	-	-	-	-	-
[Hg(NO ₃) ₂ .PBA]	36.60(36.04)	24.61	-	-	-	-	-

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

**PBA = *N*-(1-piperidinobenzyl)acetamide.

Electronic spectra : The pale pink coloured Mn^{II} complexes exhibited two weak bands at 21560–25320 cm⁻¹ assignable to ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}(G) and ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴A_{1g}(G) transitions. These are spin-forbidden transitions in an octahedral environment. The cobalt(II) chloro, bromo and nitrate com-

plexes are blue-green in colour. The reflectance spectra of the Co^{II} chloro and nitrate complexes showed multicomponent broad bands with maxima at 14815 and 14860 cm^{-1} ($\log \epsilon \sim 2.7 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) respectively, due to ${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ (ν_3) transition and the bands at 7260 and 7080 cm^{-1} respectively corresponding to ${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(F)$ (ν_2) transition. In order to calculate $10Dq$ value, interelectron repulsion parameter (Racah B) and nephelauxetic ratio (β), a series of fitting procedures summarised by Drago and Longhi⁶ was used. The nephelauxetic effect shows that B -values are lowered on complexation whereas the free metal ion values are relatively high. Jorgensen⁷ attributed the nephelauxetic effect to central field covalency and symmetry restricted covalency. The data of $10Dq$, B' , β and LFSE parameters (Table 1) suggest tetrahedral geometry for the complexes. The magnitude of β (34%) reveals the measure of covalent character in M-L bond of the Co^{II} -chloro complex. The solution spectrum of Co^{II} -bromo complex in DMF exhibited a broad band with maxima at 15950 cm^{-1} which is attributed to ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ transition in tetrahedral environment. The near-ir band was not observed in the range of instrument used.

The six-coordinated green coloured Ni^{II} -chloro complex exhibited bands at 8772, 14184 and 23810 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon = 8\text{--}60 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) assignable to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) transitions respectively. These transitions suggest a distorted octahedral environment around the central Ni^{II} ion. The lowest energy transition at 8772 cm^{-1} represents $10Dq$ energy. The Racah parameter B' value (778 cm^{-1}) is less than that for free Ni^{II} ion (1040 cm^{-1}), indicating the covalent character of the complex. The parameters ν_2/ν_1 (1.68), ν_3/ν_1 (2.71)⁸ and Dq/B (1.13) further support octahedral geometry. The nickel(II) bromo and nitrate complexes also show similar bands and their spectral parameters (Table 1) point to the distorted octahedral geometry.

The green Cu^{II} -chloro complex showed a broad band at 13128–15040 cm^{-1} with maxima at 14048 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon = 14.2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) assignable to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition. The band position and multi-component nature of the spectrum suggest a distorted octahedral geometry⁹. The copper(II) bromo and nitrate complexes exhibited similar bands with maxima at 15214 and 13820 cm^{-1} respectively, and their spectral parameters (Table 1) suggest tetragonal structure for the complexes.

Magnetic properties : The room temperature magnetic moments of the flesh-coloured Mn^{II} chloro and nitrate complexes are 5.86 and 5.77 B.M. respectively, which indicate a high-spin octahedral geometry for the complexes. The four-coordinated cobalt(II) chloro, bromo and nitrate complexes show μ_{eff} values of 4.6, 4.54 and 4.52 B.M. respectively, indicating tetrahedral environment around the central Co^{II} ion, since square-planar complexes usually show low μ_{eff} values of 2.0–3.0 B.M. The six-coordinated Ni^{II} complexes are paramagnetic with two unpaired

electrons exhibiting magnetic moments around 3.20 B.M. (Table 1) which are slightly higher than the spin-only value (2.83 B.M.). This indicates the spin-free octahedral environment around the Ni^{II} ion¹⁰. The observed room temperature magnetic moments of the mononuclear Cu^{II} complexes are 1.82, 1.91 and 2.02 B.M., which suggest a distorted octahedral geometry for the complexes.

Pmr spectra : Pmr spectrum of the ligand exhibited a multiplet signal at δ 7.6–7.3 (ArH), 5.9–5.7 (d, sec-amide N-H) and 2.6–2.4 (piperidine N- CH_2)¹¹. In Mn^{II} -chloro complex, the doublet of (N-H) proton shifted slightly downfield to δ 6.1–5.8 which reveals the coordination of carbonyl oxygen to Mn^{II} ion. The slight downfield shift of amide proton is due to less shielding of the proton since the electron pair on nitrogen is drifted towards the carbonyl group upon oxygen coordination. The signal due to piperidine (N- CH_2) protons also shifted slightly and appeared at δ 2.75 in the complex. This is an indication of the coordination of piperidine nitrogen. Thus pmr and ir results confirm the bidentate nature of PBA ligand. The pmr data of other complexes [δ 6.15–5.8 (d, sec-amide N-H) and 2.86–2.52 (m, piperidine N- CH_2)] also reveal the coordination of PBA through carbonyl oxygen and piperidine nitrogen atoms. For the 1 : 2 (M : L) complex (e.g. $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{L}_2$), the group of signals at δ 7.70–7.34 (ArH) shifted upwards in comparison to those of the free ligand and 1 : 1 complexes. From the integration values it is clear that the number of aromatic proton is double that of 1 : 1 complex.

Esr spectra : The X-band esr spectra of the Cu^{II} -chloro complex at liquid nitrogen temperature and the bromo complex at room temperature in solid state exhibited the g_{\parallel} values of 2.276 and 2.218 and g_{\perp} values of 2.074 and 2.072 respectively, as per the trend $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.04$. These indicate that the ground state of Cu^{II} ion is predominantly $\delta_{x^2-y^2}$ ¹². The g_{\parallel} value is less than 2.3 for the complexes indicating covalent nature of the complexes¹³. The spin-orbit coupling constant λ values (–496 and –459 cm^{-1} respectively) calculated by using the relations, $g_{\text{av}} = 1/3 [2g_{\parallel} + g_{\perp}]$ and $g_{\text{av}} = 2(1 - 2\lambda/10Dq)$, are less than the free Cu^{II} ion (–830 cm^{-1}) which also supports covalent character of M-L bond in the complexes. The G values of 3.80 and 3.09 indicate negligible exchange interaction among Cu^{II} centres in the complexes. The in-plane σ -bond strength represented by α^2 was calculated by $\alpha^2 = A_{\parallel}(G)/0.036 + (g_{\parallel} - 2.0023) + 3/7(g_{\perp} - 2.0023) + 0.04$, where $A_{\parallel}(G)$ is spin-Hamiltonian parameter. Since the α^2 values (0.82 and 0.69) of the complexes¹¹ are less than unity, it suggests appreciable covalency of the complexes¹³. The trend of $g_3 > g_2 > g_1 >$ of 2.304, 2.18 and 2.094 for the Cu^{II} -chloro and that of 2.267, 2.165 and 2.117 for the Cu^{II} -bromo complexes suggests an elongated rhombic octahedral geometry for the complexes¹⁴. The esr spectra of the Cu^{II} chloro and nitrate complexes recorded at room temperature show g_{iso} values only (2.11 and 2.16 respectively).

Thermal studies : The TG curves of the Mn^{II} -chloro and Zn^{II} -nitrate complexes showed initial mass loss in regions

135–165° and 130–175° respectively, corresponding to the loss of two coordinated water molecules. The DTA pattern of the chloro complex exhibited a strong endothermic peak at 145° indicating the loss of water¹⁵. The endotherm at 335–420° corresponds to the decomposition of the complex and the weak exotherm at 510° is due to the oxidation leading to the final product MnO. The Zn^{II}-nitrate complex showed a downward curve from 270 to 305° in DTG indicating decomposition of the anhydrous complex. The TG and DTG studies of the Ni^{II}-nitrate complex show that the complex is stable up to 180° and it decomposes in 180–230° and 290–310° regions. The loss of weight at 180–230° corresponds to the elimination of nitrate groups. The observed final mass at 600° corresponds to the metallic oxides. The TG pattern of the Cu^{II}-nitrate complex showed two steep curves at 200–230° and 280–305° due to decomposition. The final product at 700° is CuO. The TG curve of the Cd^{II}-chloro complex showed that the complex is stable up to 230° and 40% weight-loss occurs at 230–320° corresponding to the elimination of organic moiety of the complex. The final residue at 600° is the metal oxide.

Antimicrobial activity : The ligand PBA and its cobalt(II), nickel(II) and zinc(II) chloro complexes were tested for antibacterial activity by serial tube dilution technique¹⁶ at concentrations 300, 200 and 100 µg ml⁻¹ against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. The antimicrobial activity increased with increase in concentration of compounds. The data of maximum percentage inhibition of bacterial growth at 300 µg ml⁻¹ concentration of PBA (L) and its metal complexes are as follows : *S. aureus*, PBA 63.74, [CoCl₂.L] 78.35, [NiCl₂.L(H₂O)₂] 68.62, [ZnCl₂.L] 66.47%; *E. coli*, PBA 78.04, [CoCl₂.L] 89.26, [NiCl₂.L(H₂O)₂] 81.52, [ZnCl₂.L] 96.25%. The values reveal that the metal complexes are more active than the free ligand. The ligand and its complexes are more active towards *E. coli* than *S. aureus*. The order of activity towards *S. aureus* is Co > Ni > Zn, and towards *E. coli* Zn > Co > Ni.

Experimental

All chemicals used were either chemically pure or of A.R. grade. Solvents were distilled and dried before use.

N-(1-Piperidinobenzyl)acetamide (PBA) : Benzaldehyde was added in small quantities to the mixture of acetamide and piperidine (1 : 1 : 1 mole ratio) in ice-cold condition. The resulting colourless sticky mass was kept at room temperature for 7 days. The white solid formed was washed with water and crystallised from methanol (64%), m.p. 174–176°.

Metal complexes : The ligand being insoluble in water, all the complexes were prepared in non-aqueous media. The Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes were prepared by mixing the solution of ligand in chloroform with alcoholic solution of the metal salt in 1 : 1 mole ratio. The mixture was gently warmed on a hot water-bath. The resulting solid complex was washed with acetone and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂

under reduced pressure. The Ni^{II} complexes were prepared by similar method using ligand in chloroform and metal salt in 1-butanol in 1 : 2 mole ratio. The Co^{II} complexes were prepared by adding the ligand to metal salt in acetone medium. The Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes were obtained by stirring the mixture of methanolic solutions of the metal salt and the ligand. The complex formed was immediately filtered off and washed with acetone and dried under reduced pressure.

Metal ions and anions like chloride and bromide were estimated¹⁷ and C, H and N determined microanalytically.

Magnetic susceptibility was determined by Gouy's method at room temperature. Electronic spectra were recorded on UVIDEC-430B and Varian Cary-2390 spectrophotometers, ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 1430 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CHCl₃/DMSO-d₆) on EM-390 90 MHz and Jeol GSX 400 spectrometers and esr spectra on a Varian E-112 X-band spectrometer with DPPH as the reference material at 300 and 77 K. Conductivity was measured on a Toshniwal conductivity meter in DMF. Elemental analysis was carried out using Thomas and Coleman N analysers. Thermal data were obtained using a Shimadzu DT-40 instrument.

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